

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF ENGINEERING FIELDS IN MODERN CONSTRUCTION AND ARCHITECTURE

Parmanov.J.T.

Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction named after Mirzo Ulugbek

Abstract. *A physicist uses his knowledge and experience to study and apply the interaction of physical processes in the fields of engineering, construction, architecture, assembly work, mechanics.*

Keywords: *engineer; civil engineer, design engineer; mechanical engineer; development engineer; computer engineering specialist; applied mechanics specialist.*

Introduction

Physics teacher Provides training and education of students, taking into account the specifics of teaching the subject "Physics". Conducts lessons, additional optional classes, leads subject circles. Develops a thematic work plan on the subject, ensures the implementation of the curriculum. Participates in methodological work, uses the most effective forms, methods and teaching aids. Analyzes student activity, ensures compliance with educational discipline. This forms the skills of independent work of schoolchildren, stimulates their cognitive activity and motivation for learning. Achieves a strong and deep assimilation of knowledge on the subject, the ability to apply knowledge in practice. Equips and prepares the classroom. He studies and takes into account the individual characteristics of students in his work, participates in working with parents. Physics is one of the most complex subjects in the curriculum in higher education institutions, as it is a constantly changing scientific field. Therefore, a physics teacher must keep up with all the innovations in the world of science, familiarize himself with new discoveries, technical achievements and inventions.

The main task of a physics teacher is to teach children to understand the world around them, the processes taking place in their daily lives.

Physics is one of the most important and ancient sciences. With its help, a huge number of different processes are studied. Therefore, specialties related to physics will remain relevant for a long time. Physics is a fundamental science and is used in many areas of activity.

Physicist-engineer-A profession associated with knowledge of physical phenomena and constant practice. In this profession, it is necessary to know all mechanical processes, since this work is associated with the introduction of equipment and new technologies in various enterprises. In the event of the invention of a new technology in any research, you will have an incredible career and success. There are many directions in this field.

Physicist- A scientist whose research is mainly devoted to physics. Physicists work on a wide range of problems, from subatomic particles to the behavior of the universe.

The subject of the professional activity of a physicist is a field of science and technology that includes a combination of tools, techniques, methods and techniques for obtaining complete and reliable information about the nature and quantitative patterns of physical processes in the world, existing and new technical systems for various industries.

A physicist is engaged in the study of objects of the world and the laws of their interaction. He considers objects as physical bodies, and their interaction as physical

phenomena. Conducts physical research through experiments, builds mathematical models of physical phenomena, describes the main properties of the world. The study of physical phenomena allows physicists to discover general laws and use them for progress. For a physicist, observation and curiosity, perseverance and the desire to learn new things, patience and critical thinking, a penchant for experimentation, interest in nature and the ability to be creative in science are important. The profession requires a specialist to make mainly intellectual expenditures. The activity is associated with the analysis, comparison and interpretation of data, the development of new solutions.

The engineering profession has always been the basis of world development. The level of technical equipment determined the superiority of one civilization over another until the beginning of our era. And today it is technical innovations that ensure the development of civilization.

Today, engineering professions are the most numerous professions of highly qualified workers. More than a third of specialists with higher education in our country are engineers. An engineer participates in the production of all material goods of society - from food and consumer goods to complex computers and space rockets. A modern engineer is a highly cultured specialist who is well versed in modern engineering and technology, economics and production organization, who can use engineering methods to solve engineering problems, and at the same time has the ability to invent. The work of an engineer is a link between scientific discoveries, developments and their practical application. Engineers manage production sites at industrial enterprises, construction, agriculture and other industries, work in design bureaus, laboratories and research institutions, are engaged in the organization, planning and economics of production. They participate in the design and development of design technologies, industrial equipment, machines, production control systems, production automation, business, management processes. They study the causes of breakdowns and production failures, test products, determine their quality, etc. For full and high-quality work, an engineer needs mathematical and technical skills; analytical thinking; concentration; abstract thinking; a penchant for research; the ability to draw.

Design engineer- Engineering specialty, the activity of which is necessary for the creation and creation of a final (target) product from existing material production products and resources. Creates new objects of material culture from existing resources, organizes and technically equips the work of other people.

Design engineers create, check and edit drawings, calculate the design of structures, participate in the coordination and protection of the project, and carry out technical and architectural supervision over its implementation. The designer's duties include testing and commissioning experimental products and parts planned for future use. Develops preliminary designs, technical and working structures and products of varying complexity, organizes production processes for the production of parts and assembly machines, conducts research in the field of design, determines the technical level of manufactured products, calculates the economic efficiency of implemented projects, and draws up technical documentation for the developed design.

Mechanical engineer- a specialist with higher technical education in the field of design, construction and operation of technological equipment.

A mechanical engineer designs, builds and operates mechanical equipment, machines, devices and apparatus, automatic lines, means and systems of complex mechanization and automation of production, organizes and conducts their installation, commissioning, testing,

He develops, plans and organizes technological processes, selects optimal conditions for their implementation. His duties include planning and repairing machines, reconstructing existing ones and preparing technical specifications for the construction of new plants. In the field of agricultural production, a mechanical engineer supervises machinists, manages all mechanization of agriculture.

The main purpose of a mechanical engineer's activity is to design mechanical equipment and technological processes and organize technical maintenance of equipment.

An engineer of this specialty is a highly qualified specialist with in-depth knowledge of the theoretical foundations of electrical engineering, the theory of automatic regulation, industrial electronics and computer engineering.

Civil Engineer Works in general construction and specialized construction, construction and installation, commissioning, service, design, engineering and scientific organizations.

Carries out production and technological, organizational and management, design and research work in the field of construction. These specialists solve problems related to the design and construction of buildings and structures, water supply and sewage systems and devices, roads and pipelines, power lines and communications and other objects.

During their professional activities, a civil engineer calculates, designs and develops building structures, foundations and foundations, underground parts in various soil conditions. Develops and implements projects for the organization of construction and construction work using technologies for the production and installation of building structures, established mechanization and modern methods of labor.

A civil engineer supervises construction, installation and commissioning work, monitors their quality, exercises technical supervision over design decisions and the implementation of construction and installation works. In construction, he is engaged in the regulation of labor and budget, providing engineering support for the accounting of the self-financing brigade, draws up work orders and estimates of wages and salaries.

REFERENCES

1. <http://dic.academic.ru/>.
2. <http://www.sciencedebate2008.com/>.
3. <http://www.pravda.ru/>.
4. <http://felbert.livejournal.com/>.
5. <http://antirelativity.workfromhome.com.ua/>.
6. Mach E. Knowledge and Delusion: Essays in the Psychology of Research. - M., 1909- S. 188.
7. Nurmatov, K. D. (2023). DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM. Academic research in educational sciences, 4(3), 560-566